

Spam Identification using Machine Learning and Homomorphic Encryption

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Dissertation

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Declaration

Statement 1

This work has not been previously accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any degree.

Signed Daniel Murathodzic (2257070)

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Statement 2

This thesis is the result of my own investigations, except where otherwise stated. Other sources are acknowledged by citations giving explicit references. A bibliography is appended.

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The University's ethical procedures have been followed and, where appropriate, ethical approval has been granted.

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1 Abstract

Spam posed problems since the beginning of email communication, and Machine Learning has largely stopped them from being received en-masse. However, running Machine Learning models – which are primarily hosted on cloud services – require receiving emails in plaintext in order to run classifications, posing both privacy and security risks. Homomorphic encryption is a technique that allows for computations to be correctly made on encrypted data. We use this to allow for Machine Learning models to perform classification on encrypted emails, eliminating the privacy and security risks. We train and test 2 different models on 3 different Homomorphic encryption schemes on our spam dataset, test some optimisations to improve encrypted classification latency, and built a REST server that serves one of our models as a practical example. We found that our most efficient model was 97.05% accurate on our test data, and had a mean encrypted classification latency of 3.7ms, outperforming anything we have seen in the literature. Our results show that implementing private spam filtering at scale is practical for any email provider of any size.

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2 Introduction

2.1 Motivation

A huge number of us regularly use email. In 2024, there were approximately 4.4 billion email users and this number is expected to grow another 500 million by 2028, as cited in [16] and [78]. Alongside this, about 47% of all email traffic are classed as spam¹ [45]. Because of this large scale, spam emails have the opportunity to impact a large proportion of society, and does so negatively. Its ranging impacts include productivity losses, IT infrastructure overload (consequently with excess costs for more construction) and losses in trust from users [13]. Every year spam costs approximately \$20 billion to end users [68] while only gaining \$200 million for the spammers, an externality ratio of 100:1, which bears huge costs to society. Spam emails have also been found to manipulate stock markets [42, 35] using "pump and dump" and "scalping" strategies. Furthermore, a recent report by IBM highlights that AI is beginning to be used to augment phishing attacks, which is already the most common attack vector for data breaches- making these emails increasingly personalised with ease and subsequently more dangerous [43].

There have been many technological responses to spam, with Machine Learning (ML) techniques primarily used to classify and filter out the unwanted emails [27]. Google themselves claim to be able to filter out most spam for their gmail service [77], though it remains imperfect. While spam filtering has been a needed solution, it comes with a new problem: Privacy and Security.

With email providers effectively being a cloud service, our email contents are sent, stored and processed on their servers. Our data here inevitably risks its confidentiality and integrity [69] and it gives rise to vulnerability issues such as a cross-Virtual Machine attack, the risk of having a malicious sys-admin [81], SQL/command injections and cross-site scripting [41]. Further vulnerabilities include the application, platform, infrastructure and hardware layers of cloud systems as reviewed by Kumar et al [48] that can compromise security. When public cloud services are breached, they cost an average of \$4.68 million [43]. A survey compiled by CSA with respondents primarily identifying themselves as "Security Specialists" find that Data Breaches in the cloud is their number one concern [26]. Due to the shared nature of cloud, attacking a single provider gives access to the data of all its users [2], making these services high-value targets for attackers. When incidents do occur, digital forensics used to investigate are expensive. Investigators come up with other issues like a lack of collaboration with cross-border investigations due to differing regulations from multiple jurisdictions [31], making cloud a more attractive target. Although companies having strong privacy/encryption practices greatly improve data confidentiality with transfer and storage, it does not solve the issue completely. For these ML models to work and decide whether an incoming email is spam or not, it needs to be able to read the contents in plain text and anything already encrypted must be decrypted [71]. This includes **all messages**, even those that are valid. All emails, no matter how sensitive, will at some point be completely visible on servers elsewhere in the world, which is out of our control. This unencrypting of data leaves a serious data confidentiality issue [19].

Thankfully, a type of encryption exists known as Homomorphic Encryption (HE), allowing

¹Spam email is typically defined as anything unsolicited and unwanted by the user [77], including phishing, and can extend to it having commercial value and being sent in bulk [13].

third-parties to perform operations on the encrypted data without decrypting it [1]. This solves all the confidentiality issues noted above not just for individuals outsourcing their email communications data (or in fact any data), but also businesses/institutions themselves. HE can help companies comply with GDPR regulations too. A problem laid out on dealing with the "burden" of GDPR [15] is solved with HE. To speculate, in case of stricter future regulations, a working practical example of HE in use would likely allow companies to easily comply, avoiding further burdens.

Our project shows a practical solution to the data confidentiality issues above while still being able to largely avoid the implications that come with spam email. Although our work focuses on ML for Spam Identification, it can serve as an example for any other field that wishes to use ML on sensitive data, such as medicine, finance, government and more- due to the general applicability of HE.

2.2 Aims and objectives

The aim of our research is to experimentally explore and show working examples of ML spam classifiers that work with encrypted data using existing HE schemes.

The main objectives of this work are:

1. Train and Test two different ML Models to classify spam emails using three different HE schemes.
2. Test and analyse the predictive performances of the differing ML Models on each HE scheme.
3. Test and analyse encrypted classification latency of the differing ML Models on each HE scheme.
4. Set up a working REST api server serving one of our ML models for encrypted prediction.
5. Evaluate the practicality of using ML with HE for spam identification with our obtained results.

3 Background Research

3.1 Solving Spam Filtering

Spam filtering is typically characterised with 5 algorithmic techniques [80, 27, 36]:

1. *Content based detection technique.* The contents of an email are directly used to learn patterns that distinguish between spam and non-spam emails, which is typically done using "word analysis, occurrence analysis and distribution analysis". This includes ML models like Naive Bayesian classifier (**NB**), Support vector Machine (**SVM**), Artificial Neural Networks (**ANNs**) and K-nearest Neighbour (**KNN**).
2. *Case based detection technique.* All emails are gathered from the user's inbox, "go through pre-processing", "split into 2 different sets of vectors" so that an ML model can evaluate an incoming email based off these sets.
3. *Rule Based detection technique.* Already existing rules are used to determine the result of a new email, such that if it strongly follows a pattern for spam and receives a "high score", the result would be classified as spam. Otherwise the result classifies as non spam. Classic rule based ML models include Random Forest (**RF**) and Decision Tree classifiers (**DT**).
4. *Previous Likeness based technique.* A new email is classified based on previous examples (like training data) and is thus "memory-based". The papers note that the contents are stored in a multi-dimensional vector space, which can then be used to compare against others using K-nearest neighbours. Though generally, this technique seems to be a pre-requisite to content-based detection (since the models here would require training data to learn from) and case-based detection (where the user's emails are used as "previous likeness).
5. *Adaptive based technique.* Includes adaptive elements for ML and other algorithms such that it remains accurate and efficient as the trends of spam potentially change. This way, the solution remains dynamic rather than static. Google [77] seems to include this technique by continuously updating reputation scores from senders based on user feedback.

There also exist emerging non-algorithmic ideas that can be used as leverage for algorithmic solutions to spam filtering. This included Peer-to-Peer Computing, Grid Computing, Social Networks and Ontology-Based Semantics [14]- though the majority of papers they surveyed remained focused on algorithmic approaches themselves and is the direction we are sticking to also because of its direct applicability with HE.

The most commonly explored ML models for spam filtering include SVM, NB, KNN, RF, DT and ANN [80, 27, 36, 9].

SVMs are classed as supervised models that have strong classifying and regression capabilities along with having "good generalization" [79]. The authors compiled papers on SVM and improved versions of SVM, concluding that both are suitable for anything requiring classification. This is directly shown by Navaney *et al* [59] by achieving 98.4% accuracy when identifying spam. SVM has also been found to be useful when data is limited, at least when compared to NNs [64].

NB is a probabilistic model with a supervised learning method [80], which take advantage of probabilistic networks [30] and maintains an independence assumption. Metsis *et al* [55] examined five different versions of NB (3 of which are frequently used in the literature) and found strong recall percentages for spam and ham (legitimate non spam) at an approximate average of 95%. The results are similar to Deshpande *et al* [30], but the authors argue that the false positive rates remain too high and require augmenting the model with lemmatizers.

KNN is another supervised learning method, where distances are computed from unseen points to their k-nearest neighbours for categorisation [80]. Yeruva *et al* show an example of their work using KNN to filter spam, finding a recall percentage of 93% and Firtz *et al* show similar accuracies [34], which is then improved upon when resampling the dataset. Tusher *et al* [80] further look at few papers exploring variations of KNN, achieving slightly better accuracies to the ones above.

DT is a supervised model whose structure resembles a tree where each decision node can evaluate some value of a feature to determine its next path, until it ends at a final outcome [27], which has the benefit of assigning "unambiguous values to problems, decisions, and results of every decision". Chakraborty and Monal [17] tested three different DT models (Naive Bayes Tree, C4.5/J48 and Logistic Model Tree) but found that their accuracies were all < 90% and had false positives ranging from 14% to 34%. Subasi *et al* also tested different types of DT classifiers and scored higher overall with an accuracy of 93% for the C4.5 DT model [74]. However, this was outperformed by different types- and the best they found was the RF model.

RF is a collection of DTs, making it a "forest" [74] where its benefits come from typically obtaining fewer classification errors and "superior f-scores compared to decision trees", with its performance being comparable and often better than SVM [27]. Subasi *et al* found their RF model performing with a 95.8% accuracy [74]. Shrivatstava *et al* found their RF model perform strongly with 95.5% correctly classified instances on unseen data [73]. Cota and Zinca found their RF model to perform with 97.5% accuracy against the "spamassasin" test sets [25] and although this dropped to 85% when testing against the "input" dataset, it remained significantly higher than the other models- showing better resilience against different datasets.

ANN is a model inspired by biological neural networks [80] and has the power of approximating relationships in data. This power seems strongly effective with spam filtering. Barushka and Hajek create their own Deep NN (multiple layers) combined with pre-processing to balance the dataset and find that it performs very strongly, achieving accuracies > 98.5% across three datasets [5]. They also find that a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) (a type of ANN) also performs similarly strong. Tusher *et al* also compare two studies on varying types of NNs for spam filtering, with those achieving 94.25% and 97.92% accuracies respectively [80]. They note that this technique has better abilities in tolerating noise and discovering new patterns, with the downside of longer training times.

[36] compared the performances of most of these models, and while they all have over 90% accuracy on their spam datasets, RF performs the best, regularly over 97% accuracy- even while performing dimensionality-reduction to drastically improve training time speeds. This result supports the findings of Subasi [74] and also Shrivatstava *et al* [73], which found RF consistently outperforming the other models. However, these papers did not compare against neural network models. Barushka and Hajek did however test their NN against the more classical models [5] and

found that their NN and a CNN performed better than the rest across most datasets, but noted that RF also "achieved statistically similar performances". Overall, it seems that RF and ANN offer the best predictive performances for spam identification.

Although we have not covered all ML methods for spam filtering, these main techniques serve as the examples to follow as they are all capable of adequately classifying spam.

Of course, these solutions do not come without some glaring issues. Martino *et al* find that many existing solutions come with varying degrees of error-rates depending on the dataset used [44], noting that spammers take advantage of "adversarial ML" where they mislead classifiers by altering data and causing a "dataset shift". Returning to the upcoming trend of the use of AI in personalising these messages [43], we suspect that it could possibly further exacerbate the dataset shift issue in the future. This highlights the importance of Adaptive-based techniques to stay on top of the dynamic nature of attackers. Blanzieri *et al* [9] and Ozkan *et al* [65] also point out some evasion attacks on filters:

1. *Tokenization attacks* where spammers craft messages such that they prevent them from being correctly tokenized by the model.
2. *Obfuscation attacks* by encoding the message in a way that remains obscured to model.
3. *Statistical attacks* by purposefully skewing the statistics of the contents of the email message such that it avoids being classified negatively.

Ozkan *et al* also illustrate the dramatic predictive performance hindrances that occur when performing Tokenization and Obfuscation attacks on NB and SVM models. Though it is pointed out that the obfuscation attacks have a solution by using a Hidden Markov Model [51]. There is also a proposed solution to obfuscation with an "edit distance" algorithm [84] that slightly lowers accuracy. There unfortunately does not seem to be any direct solutions to tokenization and statistical attacks in the literature, and there are very few papers on Hidden Markov model for avoiding obfuscation in spam. Dada *et al* class the security of spam filters as an open problem [27].

3.2 Homomorphic Encryption

The first conception of HE was introduced by Rivest *et al* with their paper on privacy homomorphisms [71]. Their work communicated the possibility of performing functions on encrypted data without decrypting intermediate results. They show this by proposing two algebraic systems, one for the user and one for the computer such that encoding/decoding means mapping elements from both systems to each other. They give an example for a system of integers \mathbb{Z} where it contains its set, functions, predicate and constants- which we use to denote a user and computer to help illustrate their idea:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{User} &= \langle \mathbb{Z}; +, -, \times, \div; \leq; 0, 1 \rangle \\
 \text{Computer} &= \langle \mathbb{Z}'; +', -', \times', \div'; \leq'; 0', 1' \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

with encoding/decoding functions denoted as:

$$\phi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}'$$

$$\phi' : \mathbb{Z}' \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$$

Given some $z_1, \dots, z_i \in \mathbb{Z}$, the user can encode these elements into \mathbb{Z}' for the computer, which can perform functions on z_1, \dots, z_i without needing to decode them. When the user is sent back \mathbb{Z}' they may finally decode it back to \mathbb{Z} with a correct result. This means that the computer never sees those true values, but is still able to operate on them correctly. Concretely, if the user sends the encoded versions of numbers $enc(1), enc(2)$ for the computer to add, it returns the result $enc(3)$ which the user can correctly decode to 3.

Figure 1: Illustration of a Privacy Homomorphism in use

To put it broadly, we know an encryption scheme is homomorphic over some operation $*$, if the following holds [1]:

$$E(m_1) * E(m_2) = E(m_1 * m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M$$

where E = encryption algorithm and M = set of all possible messages

This happens because the decoding function ϕ' is a homomorphism from Computer onto User, where homomorphism is "defined as a map preserving all the algebraic structures between the domain and range of an algebraic set" as cited in [1].

Though the above mathematical example looks at integers for illustrative purposes, the idea intended to be applied to any algebraic system. However Rivest *et al* quickly found some flaws depending on the algebraic system. Notably, for a system of natural numbers with only a '+' function and a ' \leq ' predicate, a malicious actor could decode the data with a binary search strategy

[71], meaning that comparisons cannot be handled (which means the integer system example above can also be broken). There were also others they admit were difficult to spot, and came to the conclusion that these had "inherent limited applicability" because privacy cannot hold for all algebraic systems. This left them the open question of "what algebraic systems with a useful privacy homomorphism exist?".

That same year, Rivest *et al* created the well known RSA encryption that became standard for decades [70]. This was considered Partially homomorphic encryption (**PHE**) since it only supported the multiplication operation for evaluating two different encrypted messages [1]:

$$E(m_1) \cdot E(m_2) = E(m_1 \cdot m_2)$$

The problem was that an algebraic system containing only multiplication (without addition included) is limited in its applicability [1], since algorithms would only be able to include multiplication alone (the same applies for an addition only system). If both addition and multiplication were included in the system, it would allow for any operation to be performed [54]. Such system is classed as Fully Homomorphic Encryption (**FHE**). Future work to improve upon RSA came by Goldwasser and Micali [39], Benaloh [7], Paillier [66], and others that showed systems containing addition only could work. These papers and others improved upon existing PHE schemes [1], however, the same problem of limited applicability remained.

Fellows' and Koblitz's [33] work introduced their "Poly Cracker" scheme which is classed as a Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption (**SWHE**), where in addition to PHE, allowed for both addition and multiplication only limited number of times [63, 56]. Acar *et al* [1] explain that the limitation was due to an exponentially increasing size of the ciphertext. They also summarise more of the work in attempts of progress with SWHE schemes, but show that they still have limitations with respect to size and also a lot of them turning out to be broken.

A huge breakthrough arrived with the work of Gentry [37] where he proposed the first working FHE scheme using ideal lattices² and a novel bootstrapping method that allowed both addition and multiplication to be performed on the ciphertext an unlimited number of times. This solved many of the limitations from SWHE schemes, but this FHE scheme still had problems of its own. Gentry shows the bootstrapping step grows polynomially. While he shows that FHE is possible, the scheme remained practically unfeasible.

Future work now aimed to improve upon the new limitations set in place from Gentry's work [1, 56], where some new schemes moved away from ideal lattices (for simplicity) which include Learning With Error (**LWE**)³, NTRU-like and integer-based schemes. The schemes since Gentry's first solution are now all categorised into different generations, his being the first, up to the fourth generation schemes today. Marcolla *et al* [54] show the latest state-of-the-art schemes are now solely based on LWE and RLWE (Ring LWE), with the fourth generation schemes being differentiated to their second-generation counterparts by using approximation, making them much faster. The most notable of the fourth generation is the CKKS scheme, introduced by Cheon *et al* [20]. Marcolla *et al* state the most practical/widely adopted schemes include BGV [12], B/FV [32, 11] (both second generation), TFHE [24] (third generation) and CKKS [54], though no single scheme reigns completely supreme- each having their own pros and cons.

²Ideal lattices consequently make Gentry's scheme Quantum secure too [60].

³LWE schemes are also deemed quantum secure [1].

Even with the momentous progress made on HE since its first inception, implementations continue to experience limitations that stop it from gaining wide-spread adoption [1, 56, 54].

3.3 HE applied

Many of the proposed HE schemes have helpfully been implemented into open-source libraries which apply HE techniques. We have python-paillier implementing Pailliers PHE scheme in python [28]. There is SEAL from Microsoft [72] which includes FHE schemes like BGV, BFV and CKKS implementations. The openFHE library include those just mentioned and also TFHE [3]. openFHE also include hybridized options to quickly switch between schemes, reaping the benefits of the different schemes when necessary. Zama provides a TFHE library [83] and an even more helpful framework for it with concrete-ml [82] that include built-in models and also allow you to develop your own. Zama’s framework may be interesting to test since they claim their implementation provides the best inference for Deep Neural Networks [23]. There is also E3 FHE framework [22] which supports their bridging and batching techniques [21], Lattigo library [49], and many more.

As the field of HE progressed with many of the schemes being implemented as libraries, there began attempts at applying them in practice. Kocabas *et al* used the Paillier additive PHE scheme to securely calculate the average Heart Rate of a patient, and the BGV FHE scheme that implements a more complex LQTS detection feature for patients [47]. The authors found that, while both were capable of providing accurate computations, BGV could perform encryption/decryption faster than Paillier- but the required space to store the encrypted data ballooned in size, which meant having unreasonable amounts of data to transmit. Also Paillier was able to perform computations on the data 3,100 times faster than BGV, but is held back by its restrictions on computations. Chatterjee and Sengupta [18] explore translating algorithms to be able to compute on encrypted data with FHE. They work through techniques for low level encrypted operations like addition, multiplication, bitwise operations, then use these to move further- building more complex algorithms like fibonacci and encrypted data structures like stacks and queues. They also showed results for a binary search and bubble sort algorithm with an input size of 100, unfortunately showing very slow speeds of execution. Naerhig *et al* also show working examples computing averages, standard deviations and even a logistical regression model [57], showing promise for application in ML, which we explore next in section 3.4.

3.4 Related work

There exists work exploring HE’s application in ML specifically. Marcolla *et al* go through their exploration of the literature related to this, finding many examples of papers applying HE to ML models like NB, SVM, Linear/Logistic Regression and even ANNs [54].

Firstly, there are examples of work exploring the computational performance of classical ML models on some HE schemes, but typically lack insight into the predictive performance of the models themselves. We find Graepel *et al* apply a Linear Means and Fisher’s Linear Discriminant classifiers with a SWHE scheme by transforming the models into their respective polynomial approximations [40], finding an approximate slowdown of 6/7 orders of magnitude during execution. They chose to use SWHE rather than FHE, arguing the bootstrapping required by FHE

was too computationally expensive and FHE was already unnecessary for a lot of applications. While the authors explore the models' computational performance, they do not mention their models' predictive accuracies. Khedr *et al* [46] largely follow the same path. They train an NB classifier model that works with HE for detecting spam, evaluating computational performance. They do not explore any other model for classifying spam and neither communicate the NB model's classification performance. It is unclear if it was even successful. Bost *et al* deal with more ML models including NB, SVM and DT and first train their classifiers on plaintext data (since only the evaluation needs to preserve privacy), then successfully classify encrypted data [10]. Their classifiers run within seconds, which they believe is good enough in sensitive contexts. They also note that training on plaintext help avoid training times issues that would otherwise be associated with training on encrypted data, such as increasing training time with the resulting larger ciphertext. Further, they train their models against a wide range of datasets with different contexts, from breast cancer to credit card approval datasets. Like the work described above, they only evaluate their models' computational performance, leaving us unsure of its true effectiveness. Sun *et al* work with NB and DT classifiers to work with FHE, showing their implementation achieved substantial computational efficiency gains [76]. Like the papers above, they do not show model accuracies.

Nassar *et al* come up with a secure KNN model to classify encrypted image data [58]. They leverage Paillier's PHE scheme to do so and find that its predictions have better accuracies than the insecure SVM, Gaussian NB and DTs that they checked against. Unfortunately, they do not discuss the computational performance of this model. Liu *et al* have a very similar paper and insightfully discuss both predictive and computational performance [53]. They use the more modern CKKS FHE scheme to securely classify Iris data and compared the results of this to both a Paillier scheme implementation and simple plaintext- finding similar predictive performances for all. The computational performance of the CKKS KNN variant significantly outspeeds the Paillier variant, but remains slower than plaintext. Suganyandevi *et al* [75] build an SVM model with HE support for private spam filtering. They achieve an accuracy of 95.2%, but do not measure any inference latency.

Lee *et al* [50] train an NB model that is compatible with the CKKS scheme used with the lattigo HE library. They achieve accuracies of 96% and 97% on two different spam datasets, and find the computational performance to be at an acceptable level, with their quickest classification latency at 104.98ms. Badawi *et al* [4] build privFT for text classification, which uses their own implementation of the CKKS scheme and directly compare to SEAL. Their inference latency for text classification 160ms, slightly slower than Lee's results; though they compare their accuracies against other State-of-the-art models on public datasets, showing scores slightly below the best. Bian *et al* [8] classify emails with roughly 500ms latency using their hardware accelerated HE implementation, also with an NB model. Their spam recall performance is below 90% however, meaning their model fairly regularly fails to correctly classify spam when it sees it.

On more advanced ML, there have been examples of working Neural Networks using HE too. Nguyen *et al* work with an NN that classifies encrypted data specifically for spam filtering using B/FV as their FHE scheme with the SEAL library [61] while also exploring Functional Encryption. They train on plaintext data just like Bost *et al* [10]. Nguyen *et al*'s model resulted in accuracies over 95% and over 98% with vector sizes 3000 and up, however, it was severely held back by long computation times during classification evaluation. Others have also applied NNs

with HE, but these focus on image classification. Gilad-Bachrach *et al* apply a learned Convolutional NN to alternatively make classifications on encrypted image data by turning the NN into a "CryptoNet" [38], achieving accuracies of 99% with impressive speeds. The authors used a levelled HE scheme, implementing it with the SEAL library. Lee *et al*, however, note that CryptoNet does not maintain efficiency nor accuracy with more practical and advanced datasets [52]. They themselves create their own NN to classify images with TFHE with 92% accuracy and find that their speeds are slow for practical use, which contradicts the findings of Gilad-Bachrach *et al*. It is hard to tell whether the speed differences are algorithmic, or due to the computational resources available at Microsoft (the authors do not discuss this).

Overall the literature show many of types of ML models work with HE. When it comes to using classical ML models, there seem to be few papers that cover aspects of computation and predictive performance together. This is something we can explore to provide to the existing literature. Some of the papers show that training on plaintext first and then running the classifier on encrypted data is feasible. We will include this approach which may make it easier to progress on this project. There are a wide range of HE implementations in use by the works above, showing the versatility and promise of this technology. The examples of applying working classification models on encrypted data shows that it is possible to do the same. These papers combined with the many existing HE implemented libraries/frameworks (as outlined in section 3.3) gave us the confidence to attempt our own experimental evaluation of applying several ML methods to work with HE on spam identification.

4 General Project Structure

As the project grew, we decided to move out of jupyter notebooks and into a general python project, with separate multiple sub-directories and python files. A single notebook would not suffice, considering we had to preprocess data, train different models with different implementations, getting Homomorphic Encryption predictions working, and then testing and benchmarking; it was only logical to split everything up like a software project.

The project has the following main structures:

1. Data Functionality
2. Script execution
3. Saved Model Objects
4. Model Handling Classes
5. REST Server

4.1 Data Functionality

This is only concerned with the handling and managing of data. The spam dataset preprocessing is done here, giving us the needed data to train our Machine Learning models. Here we also represent classes that hold the preprocessed data, and eventually get saved to a file, so that we would only need to preprocess our data once, and use whenever.

4.2 Script Execution

Though the title may seem vague, it's exactly what we do. Since most files in our project are written as python classes, we needed somewhere that would actually build, process and execute the things we want to do; such as actually training all models, benchmarking them, running a demo, and testing that our own code works.

These separate tasks were split into their specific "scripts", which made the development of the project much easier to handle, as it let us separate and focus on different concerns at a time.

4.3 Saved Model Objects

After training our ML models, we save their objects into separate files for us to load and use at any point, allowing us to test and benchmark the models efficiently. Models are grouped into separate directories for their respective HE implementations (Zama, SEAL and PythonPaillier), with their ML names saved as the name of their file (e.g LogReg or SVM), organised for easy access.

4.4 Model Handling Classes

For the different HE libraries, we created classes that would act as a "hub" for everything we wanted to do for each implementation. That is, a place for each scheme where we could train our models and save them with the different ways the libraries allowed, so that when it came to "executing" these, we could simply call our own train/save, or any other function, and it working. Again, this was mainly to separate concerns. Each library has their own unique ways of using HE, so these classes focus on putting the pieces together and making them work.

4.5 REST Server

This is included as a "proof of practicality" that actually applying ML with HE in a real-world scenario works. The server has an endpoint set up to retrieve an incoming encrypted email, uses a model to perform an encrypted classification result and sends it back to the client in the response, with complete end-to-end encryption.

5 Details of Implementation

5.1 Data Preprocessing

To begin training any of our models, we needed to set up our data so that they were compatible with said models. Our dataset contains thousands of examples of spam and ham emails, though an ML model cannot understand what these words are, since they deal with numbers; hence the need to preprocess. We implement methods of "tokenising" our text, so that each email is represented as a vector. We chose to incorporate 2 methods to test and decide on the best one for our project: our implemented Bag of Words model (BoW) with some extra features, and Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency model (TF-IDF) that we import from sklearn.

The BoW model is a Natural Language Processing technique that solves our problem above, representing text data numerically by counting the frequency of each unique word, without considering their ordering [67]. In this case, we convert this "bag of words" to represent each unique word with a unique index, so that each email is represented as a vector with the occurring word indexes in that vector set to 1, and non occurring words to 0.

We programmed this idea into our Pre-Processing class with a few extra features. We first clean the text data up so that we represent words as least ambiguously as we can (to attempt to filter out low-signal characters/words). We remove all punctuation (alphanumeric only), turn any number into the word "number" (we do not want separate data points for each number, which would be too much; "number" alone provides enough signal for our models), and remove very common words that do not give much meaning to the content of the message, like removing "the", "and", "that", etc (which is a feature from TF-IDF).

Then we build up a frequency count for each word. We count how often each individual word occurs in the dataset, and keep only those that occur at least 200 times (Python dictionaries are leveraged for this, which lets us nicely assign counts as values, to our words as keys). Words used too infrequently tell the model very little about what classification an email deserves. Furthermore, spam emails typically use very similar words and phrasing. Removing these infrequent words ensures we focus on what is important and keeps the input data lean for efficiency.

For the words we keep, we give each an index. Each word is considered "tokenised" by being represented as an index. We create a vector the size of the total amount of words, which will represent a single email. We take an email, look at each word, find what index they represent, and change that specific index in the vector to the number 1. We do this for all words. In the end, the vector will have 0's and 1's, with the 1's corresponding to the words used in the email. This process is done for all emails, so we end up with vectors that both correctly represent their emails and are directly compatible for training our ML models.

$$\mathbf{Email}_i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The TF-IDF model is similar to BoW, keeping words without care for ordering. However, this model measures the importance of each word by balancing the frequency of the word in a document with its rarity in the collection of documents (inverse frequency), giving more weight to meaningful words and less weight to those less meaningful – distinguishing signal from noise in text well.

We use scikit's TfidfVectorizer to use these NLP features to both compare against BoW and use in our final HE models.

5.2 ML with HE

We directly implement three Homomorphic Encryption libraries. Zama’s concrete ML, using their TFHE scheme [82]; TenSEAL, built on top of Microsoft SEAL, which allows to use its features with python while maintaining the performance of c++ code [6]; and Python Paillier, an older, PHE scheme implemented for use with python [28].

With these schemes, we chose to use the Logistic Regression and SVM models to train, run encrypted inference, and compare between each other and each scheme. All our models were trained on plaintext data, and then given encrypted data for testing.

5.2.1 ConcreteML

This is zama’s Machine Learning framework built to work directly with their HE scheme for guaranteed privacy preserving model training and inference. It works similarly to the sklearn library that allows data scientists to train and run ML models without having to write the algorithms themselves. Concrete ML gives you a selection of models in the same manner – you call with only a few functions to set up.

We placed all functionality in our ZamaModels class. We set up model training, keeping the model quantization to 8 bits (which is required by the scheme); saving the model, keeping model and the client cryptographic specification associated in their own directories (for logistic regression, or svm); compiling model HE circuits; loading the model; generating client private keys; and testing methods to ensure correctness.

Implementation here is fairly straight forward, since the function calls are all listed in their documentation. We primarily wrap the available methods into a class to contain the main functionality for what we need.

After all models are trained and saved, each preprocessed and vectorised email is encrypted with client generated private keys. This encrypted email is simply given into the model as input, and the model produces an encrypted prediction, which you decrypt with the client keys to get the plaintext classification result.

5.2.2 TenSEAL

This library allows us to directly perform operations like addition and multiplication on encrypted vectors, which also include the dot product and matrix multiplication. Unlike ConcreteML, the library contains only these primitive building blocks, requiring us to implement the ML models ourselves and then applying these encrypted compatible operations.

We implement both models leveraging pytorch to perform the derivative calculations for the gradient descent, so that the weights and bias of both models are updated towards a continuously lower loss function.

Our Logistic Regression utilises the Binary Cross Entropy loss function (handled by pytorch):

$$-\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)]$$

And our SVM's soft-margin loss, which we implement:

$$\|w\|^2 + C\left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \max(0, 1 - y_i(w^\top x - b))\right]$$

With these loss functions, we train these models in 3000 and 2200 epochs respectively to minimise our loss functions for final values of w and b .

Further, both models utilise the boundary equation for classification:

$$w^\top x - b$$

where the w represent the model weights, and are of the same dimension/length as the input data x – which is our email; and b as the bias.

Since HE allows for operations to be performed between plain data and encrypted data, we set up our model objects to contain their weights and bias, and perform a prediction by computing the dot product of the weight and encrypted data and subtracting the bias. We call this our preliminary prediction:

$$w^\top \text{enc}(x) - b$$

We let our Logistic Regression and SVM models do encrypted inference on this equation alone primarily for maintaining efficiency and privacy. Logistic Regression requires us to run this preliminary result through a sigmoid function for final classification:

$$\frac{1}{1 + e^x}$$

The problem here is that x is encrypted. We cannot just multiply e^x amount of times, because we (or the server) do not know x . The only way to compute this would be to use the Taylor-series polynomial approximation (which can multiply the encrypted x to powers of known plain numbers). Instead of performing these extra computations however, we finish the encrypted result, send it back to the client, and have them decrypt and compute the sigmoid for a final classification much more efficiently.

For our SVM, the final prediction is determined by whether our final value is positive or negative. This is not possible to do without decrypting the values on the server, so we send the preliminary result back, the client decrypts and can instantly compute the classification.

It is up to us to set up encryption key parameters. SEAL offers multiple different HE schemes within the library. We select the CKKS scheme because it functions with the set of real numbers (\mathbb{R}), which lets the models to continue to use floating point numbers, and subsequently allowing them to be accurate and avoid having to deal with potentially large integers. We set up 2 sets of encryption parameters: 1 for the full preprocessed vector input, and the other for our dimension-reduced input (more detail in 5.3). The polynomial modulus degree is set at 2^{14}

and 2^{12} respectively. These define the size of our ciphertexts, with the lower sizes equating to more efficient encryption operations. 2^{14} was the smallest we could fit our non-reduced input, primarily due to the high dimensionality (3020). Conversely, fitting our reduced input (150 dimensions) allows for the smaller ciphertext space, and dramatically speeds up inference (which we discuss in our results: 6.2.2).

5.2.3 PythonPaillier

The manual work with TenSEAL allowed for the paillier library to be easily incorporated, since it strictly provides the basic encrypted operations alone, including the needed dot product (the additive scheme allows for this). We used our trained Logistic Regression and SVM models weights and biases, and added these to a separate class that also allowed the preliminary prediction using this libraries own dot product operation. The same reasons for the preliminary predictions in TenSEAL apply here too.

Like in TenSEAL, the key length affects the efficiency and security of encryption. We placed the key length to 2048 bits (2^{11}), because the minimum recommended bit security for applications is now 112 bits until 2030, due to modern computers being better able to perform prime factorisation [62].

Encrypted inference is done in a very similar manner to our TenSEAL models. We run encrypted inference by generating private keys, encrypting a specific vectorised email and pass this into the models preliminary prediction to compute the dot product of $w^T enc(x)$ and subtract by b , to return for the client to decrypt and evaluate with the same sigmoid function for Logistic Regression and the absolute function for SVM.

5.3 Model Optimisation

We make use of 2 dimensionality reduction models offered by sklearn: PCA and Truncated SVD. The point being to dramatically cut down the size of each email. TruncatedSVD is included, since it could offer benefits for our model accuracies in text beyond PCA by helping to capture different words that mean the same thing (synonyms) [29].

For both BoW and TF-IDF, we get 3020 dimensions per vectorised email, so reducing this was the most obvious optimisation we could make, since the size directly affects the number of encrypted computations made.

Very importantly, we fit each model to the training data, then transform both training and test data (fitting to test data causes data leakage). The fitting and transform was first done with a large amount of components in order to check how much variance is explained by each component, so that we can decide on the best size; then save the final n-dimensional data to train our "optimised" models on (more detail in 5.5).

The reduced data is saved to a separate directory to be later loaded for training new models on this input.

5.4 Client and REST Server

We use the *FastAPI* library in python to set up the REST server. This way it integrates seamlessly with the rest of the project, allowing us to easily import all our models and functions to use for the backend. For the client, we use the *requests* library to send the specific http requests to the server endpoints.

Only a POST request endpoint is used to receive encrypted data from a client. The client encrypts a specific email from the test set and serialises both the email and public evaluation keys, and sends a POST request by packaging these into 2 separate binary payloads using http's 'application/octet-stream', which handles transport of binary data. The server receives both packages, deserialises the email using the evaluation key, and performs a server-side encrypted prediction. The encrypted result is then serialised again and sent back to the client within the response content, again with octet-stream. The client then deserialises, decrypts and quickly computes the final classification result.

Below are examples of what the client/server code looks like:

Client:

```
1 binary_data = enc_email_and_pub_key()
2
3 response = requests.post(
4     base_url + "spamfilter/",
5     files=binary_data
6 )
7
8 if response.status_code == 200:
9     enc_result_bytes = response.content
10    enc_result = enc_result_bytes.deserialize(private_key)
11    result = enc_result.decrypt()
```

Server:

```
1 @app.post("/spamfilter")
2 async def encrypted_prediction(
3     pub_key_file: UploadFile = File(...),
4     enc_email_file: UploadFile = File(...)
5 ):
6     pub_key_bytes = await pub_key_file.read()
7     enc_email_bytes = await enc_email_file.read()
8
9     pub_key = pub_key_bytes.deserialize()
10    enc_email = enc_email_bytes.deserialize(pub_key)
11
12    enc_result = model.enc_prediction(enc_email)
13    enc_result_bytes = enc_result.serialize()
14
```

```
return Response(content=enc_result_bytes, media_type="
    application/octet-stream")
```

Note that this whole process is done without the server ever seeing the original email contents. Without the private key – which the client never sends – they have no way of decrypting the ciphertext. The result is completely evaluated correctly solely on this encrypted data.

5.5 Testing

The main focus here is our ML model performance when dealing with encrypted data. This includes its predictive performance against our testing data, and the time it takes to perform each classification (latency).

For predictive performance, we include scores for accuracy, precision, recall and F1. So not only will we get a simple result for how often our model predicts correctly, we will also get a good idea of what each model's strengths and weaknesses are. Although our dataset is very balanced at almost 50/50 between ham and spam email, we aim to maintain rigour and give a complete picture to readers.

We test predictive performance against the plaintext version of our models. Though this may sound contradictory, we note 2 reasons: classification on encrypted data mathematically yields the same results as plaintext data, and in a lot of cases, running classification on the full encrypted test set is too slow.

To make sure our encrypted predictions are actually equivalent, we select 30 random emails from the test set and evaluate predictions from both the plaintext and encrypted texts to see if the same model is classifying them equally. We run this several times for each model to ensure that encrypted classification is working correctly.

For testing encrypted classification latency, we employ some typical statistical measures. Since classifying the whole encrypted test set can take too long, we again select a smaller random sample of 33, though we drop the first 3 results in case of cold-starts from our hardware effecting the results. We pick this sample size of 30, because the central limit theorem states that a large enough sample "means" follow a normal distribution. This requires a sample size of at least 30. Therefore, we stick with this so that we can calculate confidence intervals for the mean time taken per classification.

We use python's `time.perf_counter()` before and after calling our model's `classify` function to measure the total time taken in milliseconds. Each classification is stored in a list. With this list, we calculate mean, standard deviation and variance of our results. Then we calculate an error margin to give us a 95% Confidence Interval, so we can be confident that the average classification times for most emails lie with our result:

$$1.96 \frac{SD}{\sqrt{N}}$$

We also test time taken for client encryption/decryption.

We also test several parts that later affect the results of our main accuracy and latency tests. Firstly, deciding on our preprocessing method. We compare the predictive accuracy of our models trained on our Bag of Words implementation with scikit's Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method, so that we select the best one. Further, we compare 2 different dimensionality-reduction techniques: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and TruncatedSVD, to select the one that offers better optimisations. Scree plots are used to check variance explained, and again, we train models on each and compare their accuracies.

To ensure software correctness (since our codebase grew larger than anticipated), we create separate files to test and confirm correctness before running any benchmarks or demos. E.g, ensuring we save and load our models correctly, that they used the correct preprocessed data, etc.

For our REST server, we make use of FastAPI's built in docs to view and manage our endpoints, and its server logs to see what happens when we engage with the endpoints. We also set up 2 usage measurements. CPU usage with the psutil library, which tells us how much usage in (%) a single core is using; and the tracemalloc library to measure peak memory usage in Megabytes. This way, we can see how much resources a server needs so we get a good idea of how our project would handle real-world scenarios.

6 Results

6.1 Preliminary testing

6.1.1 Dimensionality reduction analysis

Since a primary concern is the efficiency of HE computations, we first explored reducing dimensions on our dataset, and to later test how these effect final model classification accuracies. To reason about how many dimensions we ought to reduce with PCA/SVD, we created a scree plot to visualise how much variance each component explained:

Figure 2: Scree plot

Both models are almost identical, apart from the 2nd component for SVD explaining even more than its first. We can see that the inflection point begins quickly in the 12-25 component range, and largely flattens after 100. Note however, how low the variance explained is. The first is at 8%, which very quickly drops to below 1%. Hence we plotted the accumulated variance explained, shown below:

Figure 3: Cumulative Scree plot

Each component generally captures weak signals, which is to be expected with human language. The question here is whether these low cumulative variances capture enough signal for the model to distinguish between spam and ham emails. Since there are negligible differences seen between the PCA and SVD variances, we train our models on both methods on a range of components from 50 to 300, which explains 20% and 50% variance respectively to see how classification accuracy is effected. We also test these reductions on both BoW and TF-IDF vectors to also see how each NLP method effect model accuracy on the reduced data too. This way, we can see the effects of all the optimisation parts combined, and select the best combination.

6.1.2 BoW vs TF-IDF

We used zama’s plaintext Logistic Regression and SVM models as the testers for the effectiveness of BoW vs tf-idf. The dimensionality reductions with PCA/SVD are also included to see how each NLP model effects each, both using 200 components as the baseline comparison.

Table 1: Comparison of Model Accuracy Performance (%)

Metric	Baseline	PCA 200	SVD 200
Log BoW	97.95	96.6	96.6
Log tf-idf	98.45	97.55	97.55
SVM BoW	97.75	96.2	96.7
SVM tf-idf	98.7	98.05	97.8

As illustrated, the tf-idf representations outperform our BoW implementation. The baseline improvements for Logistic Regression is +0.5% and +0.95% for SVM. The improvements on dimensionality reduction are even greater. Logistic Regression on tf-idf has +0.95% and +1% improvement over BoW for PCA and SVD respectively. SVM on tf-idf showed even more improvement with +1.85% and +1.2% for PCA/SVD. Not only is tf-idf more accurate, but more importantly there is better optimisation with dimensionality reduction. Thus we decided to continue the project using tf-idf alone.

Our initial testing showed little difference between PCA and SVD in final plaintext accuracy, so we further investigated the differences on tf-idf with different component lengths to see how PCA and SVD behave. We set up 5 different blocks [50, 100, 150, 200, 300] of components, and trained the models on each with PCA and SVD:

Table 2: Dimensionality Reduction Accuracies (%) with tf-idf

Metric	50	100	150	200	300
Log PCA	96.95	97.25	97.4	97.55	97.85
Log SVD	96.95	97.35	97.6	97.55	97.9
SVM PCA	97.0	97.35	97.55	98.05	98.2
SVM SVD	97.1	97.5	97.75	97.8	98.25

Apart from Logistic Regression’s PCA and SVD having the same accuracy at 50 and 200 components, and SVM’s PCA performing +0.25% better than SVD at 200 components – SVD slightly outperforms PCA for both models across all other component lengths. Because of this, we make use of the TruncatedSVD model alone for our optimised encrypted model testing. We chose the 150 components for training our ‘optimised-version’ models because we believe it gives us the best balance of reduction and maintaining accuracy. With Log and SVM combined, it has the same accuracy as the 200 component version and less than 1% loss from the original text accuracies, which is an excellent trade-off for the latency improvements we see in our main results.

6.2 Main Results

6.2.1 Classification Reports

Below we list the tables of classification reports for all our trained models. Tables on the left include only models trained from the full training data. Tables on the right are trained on our TruncatedSVD reduced data to 150 components.

Table 3: Zama Logistic Regression report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	99.49	97.38	98.42
Spam	97.47	99.50	98.48
Accuracy	98.45		

Table 4: Zama optimised LR report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	98.86	96.27	97.55
Spam	96.42	98.91	97.65
Accuracy	97.60		

Table 5: Tenseal/Paillier LR report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	99.06	95.97	97.49
Spam	96.15	99.11	97.61
Accuracy	97.55		

Table 6: Tenseal/Paillier optimised LR report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	98.64	95.26	96.92
Spam	95.49	98.71	97.07
Accuracy	97.00		

Table 7: Zama SVM report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	99.49	97.88	98.68
Spam	97.95	99.50	98.72
Accuracy	98.70		

Table 8: Zama optimised SVM report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	98.66	96.77	97.71
Spam	96.88	98.71	97.79
Accuracy	97.75		

Table 9: Tenseal/Paillier SVM report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	99.59	96.88	98.21
Spam	97.00	99.60	98.29
Accuracy	98.25		

Table 10: Ts/Pail optimised SVM report

	Precision	Recall	f1
Ham	98.95	95.06	96.97
Spam	95.32	99.01	97.13
Accuracy	97.05		

Overall, all models perform strongly over the test set – though there are many observations to point out. Firstly, the zama models are superior to our own built models (that TenSEAL and Paillier use). This is not a surprise, since there are likely many optimisations that we have missed which are already considered in the zama. But our models are respectively close. Our Logistic Regression is -0.9% worse than zama’s, and the optimised version is even closer at -0.6%. For SVM, we have -0.45% behind zama’s, and -0.7% for its optimised version.

The best result is arguably the recall scores for spam for all models. A high recall score tells us that models are exceptional at flagging spam when it sees real spam emails. For the base

models, all recall scores are above 99%, the highest being our own SVM model with 99.6%. In most instances, users would not be receiving spam, which is the whole point of spam filtering. The optimised models still maintain high 98% and one 99% recall on spam, so it would still be strongly effective.

The caveat is the models suffer slightly with false positives. The recall scores for Ham emails hover around 96-98% for base models and 95-97% for the optimised, meaning there are instances of genuine Ham emails being flagged as Spam that we would consider too frequent. You can observe the inverse relation with precision, with lower scores for spam (classifying ham as spam more often), but high scores for ham (not many spam are classified as ham).

6.2.2 Latency Results

These results were measured on the following hardware specification:

Hardware Component	Specification
System on Chip (SoC)	Apple M1 (5nm TSMC)
CPU	8-Core (4x Performance, 4x Efficiency)
CPU Clock Speed	3.2 GHz (Performance) / 2.06 GHz (Efficiency)
GPU	8-Core (Up to 2.6 FP32 TFLOPS)
Neural Engine (NPU)	16-Core (11 INT8 TOPS)
Memory	8 GB Unified Memory (LPDDR4X-4266)

Table 11: Hardware specification of Apple M1 chip

Model encrypted prediction latency time per email on the left and their respective encryption/-decryption latency times per email on the right. The optimised data versions (150 component svd) are denoted with an o-name. Plaintext versions denoted with p-name. All results come from a sample size of 30.

Table 12: Zama prediction latency

	Latency (ms) $\pm 95\%$ CI
LR	209.0 \pm 2.6
SVM	195 \pm 1
o-LR	18.1 \pm 0.1
o-SVM	19.1 \pm 0.2
p-LR	0.05 \pm 0.01
p-SVM	0.06 \pm 0.02

Table 13: Zama enc/dec latency

	Latency (ms) $\pm 95\%$ CI
Enc	190.0 \pm 0.3
Dec	0.71 \pm 0.02
o-Enc	8.49 \pm 0.02
o-Dec	0.70 \pm 0.01

Table 14: Tenseal prediction latency

	Latency (ms) $\pm 95\%$ CI
LR	96.3 \pm 0.4
SVM	94.3 \pm 1.7
o-LR	3.73 \pm 0.05
o-SVM	3.70 \pm 0.05
p-LR	0.10 \pm 0.02
p-SVM	0.11 \pm 0.01

Table 15: Tenseal enc/dec latency

	Latency (ms) $\pm 95\%$ CI
Enc	5.24 \pm 0.02
Dec	0.94 \pm 0.01
o-Enc	1.29 \pm 0.01
o-Dec	0.10 \pm 0.01

Table 16: Paillier prediction latency

	Latency (ms) $\pm 95\%$ CI
LR	875 \pm 16
SVM	821.0 \pm 3.5
o-LR	38.3 \pm 0.3
o-SVM	38.8 \pm 0.4
p-LR	0.10 \pm 0.02
p-SVM	0.11 \pm 0.01

Table 17: Paillier enc/dec latency

	Latency $\pm 95\%$ CI
Enc (s)	20.4 \pm 0.2
Dec (ms)	2.1 \pm 0.2
o-Enc (ms)	984.0 \pm 11.0
o-Dec (ms)	1.83 \pm 0.02

Observe the large variations in model latency times between the different schemes and their optimised and plaintext versions. The CKKS scheme implemented by the SEAL library largely outperforms both zama and paillier. The baseline models are $\sim 2x$ faster than zama and $\sim 9.5x$ faster than paillier. The optimised versions are even more impressive for TenSEAL. At $\sim 3.7ms$ per prediction, it is $\sim 5x$ faster than the optimised zama models, and $\sim 10x$ faster than paillier.

Encryption latencies tell the same story. TenSeal is ahead by huge margins, with $\sim 5ms$ and $\sim 1ms$ (optimised), it is $\sim 38x$ and $\sim 8x$ faster than zama and $\sim 4000x$ and $\sim 984x$ faster than paillier. The decryption times are all quick for all schemes, which is expected.

These results show how much improvement the modern libraries have made over Paillier’s scheme, considering they support Fully Homomorphic Encryption. In our case, even though FHE is not needed, the new schemes largely outperform Paillier, and TenSEAL offers very competitive latencies, largely caused by the reduction of the polmod degree to 2^{12} , to which our 150 dimensional input fits in. Further, we can see how much speed gains there are training models on reduced dimension datasets. Despite our quickest model being $\sim 37x$ slower than its plaintext counterpart, the speeds are quick enough that it gives rise to the very serious plausability of practical application in the real world.

6.2.3 Server usage results

We built a working REST API server that utilises our fastest TenSEAL SVM model trained on SVD-reduced data. Below is our measured CPU (100% = 1 core) and Peak-Memory usage between receiving a POST request from a client and sending a response:

Table 18: Server usage

Peak-Memory (MB)	CPU (%) $\pm 95\%$ CI
65.91	94.8 \pm 1.1

7 Reflection

7.1 Product Evaluation

7.1.1 Comparison against literature

We find 4 papers that are most relevant for comparison, utilising classification models that work with HE to predict spam.

Nguyen *et al* [61] created a Neural Network with 95% accuracy and 265s classification latency under encryption. Lee *et al* [50] built a Naive Bayesian model with 96% and 97% on 2 different spam test sets, and achieved their quickest encrypted prediction latency of 104.98ms. Finally, Bian *et al* [8] classify encrypted emails with roughly 90% recall on spam, and with 500ms latency using thier hardware accelerated HE implementation. Finally, Badawi *et al* [4] built privFT, which uses their own implementation of the CKKS scheme and found that their latency for text classification to be 170ms for their encrypted emails, though they do not show any accuracy scores for this same test set.

Our fastest implementation of Logistic Regression and SVM, trained on SVD reduced data to 150 dimensions has higher accuracies than the 3 papers’ scores, with 97% and 97.05% accuracy, along with 98.71% and 99.01% spam recall. Mean encrypted prediction latency is 3.73ms and 3.7ms respectively, significantly faster than the best result of the 4 papers.

It is important to note that these results are not perfectly comparable. Firstly, the papers use different datasets to train their models. Our models accuracy scores may not be fairly comparable to theirs. Secondly, the papers used different hardware when testing latency, which greatly effect the speeds depending on what you use. For example, Lee uses an Intel 10400F desktop chip with 32GB memory. Bian uses an IntelXeon E5-2630 2.3 GHz processor on a single core with 32 GB memory. Both of these are older than the apple m1 chip, so our latency speeds are likely to be inflated simply due to hardware improvements.

However, despite the un-even comparisons, final performance is what matters. On a 2020 laptop chip, with our optimisations, we were able to achieve speeds $\sim 28x$, $\sim 46x$ and $\sim 135x$ faster than Lee, Badawi and Bian. Using a state-of-the-art chip from 2026 would yield even better improvements, which is directly relevant for practical applications today. To the best of our knowledge, we are the only ones to achieve encrypted classification latency of less than 5ms for spam identification with little accuracy loss, and are the only ones to consider dimensionality reduction optimisations to achieve these speed ups.

7.1.2 Implications

This project has shown that providing completely private spam filtering services is not only achievable, but also practical. The biggest bottleneck with HE was its inefficient computational performances. We have shown that now, this bottleneck is close to being negligible.

Consider a business providing an email service that includes spam filtering. Assume they have 10 million users, and each of those users receive on average 100 emails a day, they would require running ML classifications on 1 billion emails per day.

At 3.7ms per encrypted classification, they can classify the below number of emails:

$$\begin{aligned}1000/3.7 &\approx 270/\textit{persecond} \\60 \times 270 &= 16,200/\textit{perminute} \\60 \times 16,200 &= 972,000/\textit{perhour} \\24 \times 972,000 &= 23,300,000/\textit{perday}\end{aligned}$$

This is only for a single model.

$$1,000,000,000 \div 23,300,000 = 43$$

Service providers would only require 43 concurrent processes to handle 1 billion daily emails. Even with our hardware, our model has a mean 94.8% cpu usage on 1 core and approximately 66MB peak-memory usage. With 8 cores, we can run 8 encrypted classifications concurrently with peak memory usage at 528MB.

$$\left\lceil \frac{43}{8} \right\rceil = 6$$

Thus, with our hardware, 6 separate dedicated server machines running our optimised TenSEAL SVM model can handle the load of classifying 1 billion encrypted emails daily. If a service has 10 billion encrypted emails daily (100 million users), they would need 60 machines. If they have 100 billion encrypted emails daily (1 billion users, the likes of gmail and icloud), they would need 600 machines.

Even with our 6 year old hardware, a company would have zero issues setting up the infrastructure needed to even deal with the scale the biggest email providers see. This is without considering what the latest hardware is capable of.

There is zero doubt that spam filtering with Machine Learning and end-to-end encryption at scale is possible. We believe this project and our results show that the future of providing services with complete end-to-end encryption is very near, and serves as an example to researchers, engineers, and companies to further investigate and consider implementing this technology.

7.2 Process Evaluation

We believe this project was successful, especially considering our aims and objectives from our planning document. At first, we set out to build 2 ML models with at least 2 separate HE libraries. We did so with 3 HE libraries, and consequently had more results to compare against each other. We successfully benchmarked both predictive performances and classification latency for all models on all schemes. We went on to further add some optimisations to our models and showed that deploying encrypted spam identification is possible at large scales. Further, we also built a quick REST server to showcase and prove practicality. In the end, we got more done than we had originally planned, and we believe we obtained important results and realisations with strong implications. With all this combined, there is still plenty to improve upon.

Firstly, we could have expanded our datasets. Though we were kindly given one by our supervisor, we realise there are plenty more publicly available datasets that many of the papers we discussed used. Not only could we have trained our models on much more data, we could have also specifically trained them with the same datasets as other papers to directly compare against their model accuracies. This would have made our results comparisons much more rigorous. With that, we could have then applied hypothesis testing to validate any improvements if they were made. A more expanded and diverse dataset here would have also reduced the risk of training on poisoned datasets, or those with dataset-drift, which would help make our models more resilient and improve accuracy on unseen data.

Another improvement we could have made is finding ways to either adjust our compared latency times to the literature to account for hardware differences, or directly accessing the same hardware as what the papers used and run separate tests to get a fair comparison, then applying hypothesis testing again to confirm any improvements. That way, we could be certain that we made some real and serious optimisation gains without it being completely explained by hardware improvements. This change is certainly achievable with both more time and resources. At the same time, we think that we could have made our results much more relevant as of 2026 by also testing latency times on the latest hardware. These have improved a lot since 2020, and using something more modern would have made these results even more realistic and relevant and certainly faster.

We also think that there was more effort to be made in further optimising our ML models. Although we had strong accuracies on our test set, and made huge latency improvements with SVD reduced-dimensions data, there is plenty to continue researching about in this domain. There are likely many non-obvious optimisations to be made that we missed out on – though this improvement is less realistic than the others, given that ML optimisation could be a research project all on its own. Regardless, we think that our fastest model is only the tip of the iceberg, where we could potentially leverage any improvements in the latest NLP techniques for better accuracies, and utilising modern low-level hardware to make use of the latest GPUs or neural engines for vastly more efficient matrix and vector computations. Further improvements are especially important for anyone planning to deploy private spam filtering in practice, where small improvements in both speed and accuracy make huge differences at scale.

Alongside this, more types of existing ML models could have been explored. We only looked into Logistic Regression and SVM, though there are many more that can have the potential to lead to some important results.

8 Conclusion

Of all models trained, we produced accuracies that ranged from 97-98.7% on our spam test set. We found major improvements on the more modern Fully Homomorphic encryption schemes, with the use of the TenSEAL library resulting in the fastest encrypted classification latency, followed by zama, then Paillier far behind both. Utilising TF-IDF over BoW gave us the best predictive performance, and lead to lower accuracy losses with our dimensionality reductions. We also found that the TruncatedSVD offered better model predictive performance over PCA, and was the primary reason behind our 3.7ms encrypted classification latency with TenSEAL. Our results imply real-world practicality of private spam filtering at large scales, allowing for mass privacy, data confidentiality, and the reduction of many security risks that come with needing to decrypt user data to perform computations. Our project was limited by potentially unfair comparisons to other research papers: using different datasets for training and accuracy testing, and different hardware for latency testing. At the same time, our own hardware is relatively outdated, which may not give the clearest upper bound for what computational performances are possible. Future work must address these issues, allowing for clear, fair and certain comparisons to the literature; and at the same time, make use of the latest and greatest hardware along with low level optimisations to push performance in order to expand the possibilities of Homomorphic Encryption application.

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